

Effectiveness of Health Education Videos on Knowledge of Preventive Care for Foot Wounds in Diabetes Patients: A Systematic Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Based on data from the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), in 2024, 106.9 million adults aged 20-79 years in Southeast Asia will develop diabetes. This number is estimated to increase by 73%, reaching 185 million people by 2050. This increase in cases continues to occur due to problems in producing insulin so that cells cannot receive glucose for metabolism. The purpose of this study was to determine the effectiveness of health education videos on knowledge of foot wound prevention care in diabetic patients. The method in this study used a Systematic Literature Review, searching for data or information sources through Google Scholar, then conducting selection through quality assessment with inclusion and exclusion criteria. The results of the study showed that the initial level of knowledge of diabetes patients, especially regarding foot care and wound prevention, was in the category of poor to very poor before educational interventions were given. After education, there was a significant increase in the level of knowledge after providing education using video/digital media. The conclusions collectively confirm that educational videos or digital/audiovisual media are highly effective and relevant intervention methods for increasing patient knowledge and behavioral intentions for foot ulcer prevention. This increased understanding is key to fostering patient awareness and self-care skills, which ultimately reduces the risk of serious complications such as diabetic foot ulcers.

Keywords : Foot Wounds, Diabetes, Education, Video.

ABSTRAK

Berdasarkan data International Diabetes Federation (IDF) pada tahun 2024 sebanyak 106,9 Juta orang dewasa usia 20-79 tahun di Asia Tenggara menghasilkan diabetes. Angka ini diperkirakan meningkat sebesar 73% yaitu mencapai 185 juta jiwa pada tahun 2050. Peningkatan kasus ini terus terjadi karena masalah dalam memproduksi insulin sehingga sel tidak bisa menerima glukosa untuk metabolisme. Tujuan Penelitian ini adalah untuk mengetahui efektivitas video edukasi kesehatan terhadap pengetahuan perawatan pencegahan luka kaki pasien diabetik. Metode dalam Penelitian ini menggunakan jenis penelitian Tinjauan Sistematis (*Systematic Literature Review*), pencarian data atau sumber informasi melalui *google scholar*, kemudian melakukan seleksi melalui penilaian kualitas dengan kriteria inklusi dan eksklusi. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan dari 5 artikel yang di review bahwa tingkat pengetahuan awal pasien diabetes, khususnya mengenai perawatan kaki dan pencegahan luka, berada dalam kategori kurang hingga sangat kurang sebelum intervensi edukasi diberikan. Setelah dilakukan edukasi menunjukkan adanya peningkatan signifikan pada tingkat pengetahuan setelah pemberian edukasi menggunakan media video/digital. Kesimpulan bahwa secara kolektif menegaskan bahwa video edukatif atau media digital/audiovisual merupakan metode intervensi yang sangat efektif dan relevan untuk meningkatkan pengetahuan dan niat perilaku pencegahan luka kaki pada pasien. Peningkatan pemahaman ini menjadi kunci untuk memicu kesadaran dan kemampuan pasien dalam melakukan perawatan diri (self-care), yang pada akhirnya akan menurunkan risiko terjadinya komplikasi serius seperti Diabetic Foot Ulcer.

Kata Kunci : Luka Kaki, Diabetes, Edukasi, Video

INTRODUCTION

Background

According to data from the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), 106.9 million adults aged

20-79 in Southeast Asia will have diabetes by 2024. This figure is projected to increase by 73%, reaching 185 million by 2050. This continued increase in cases is due to problems with insulin production, which

prevents cells from absorbing glucose for metabolism. Diabetes is a global health issue of particular concern, as nearly half the world's population suffers from diabetes and approximately 3.4 million deaths are attributed to the disease (IDF, 2025).

According to the Indonesian Ministry of Health's Basic Health Research (Riskesdas) data, the prevalence of diabetes in Indonesia increased from 6.9% to 8.5% between 2013 and 2018. This increase is attributed to unhealthy lifestyles, but diabetes also occurs due to hereditary factors. Hereditary factors, coupled with unhealthy lifestyle choices such as lack of physical activity, obesity, hypertension, smoking, and an unbalanced diet, will exacerbate the problem (Kemenkes RI, 2025).

Diabetes affects the foot or diabetic foot ulcers, which can lead to amputation, reduced quality of life, and increased risk of death. Therefore, treatment requires early detection to prevent diabetic foot ulcers (Agustini et al., 2024).

Diabetes is a rapidly increasing cause of death worldwide. Many people with diabetes experience limb amputations. Some complications include coronary artery disease, nephropathy, retinopathy, and the most common, diabetic neuropathy, nerve damage caused by diabetes. High blood sugar levels can damage nerves in the feet, causing numbness, tingling, or pain. This can make sufferers unaware of injuries or pressure, allowing even small wounds to develop (Emeliawati et al., 2025).

The government has made various efforts to address the problem of diabetes, which causes diabetic foot ulcers. One of these efforts is through the Decree of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia No. HK.01.07/MENKES/2009/2024, which regulates guidelines for preventing diabetes in children. Prevention should be carried out by providing education about the risk factors, symptoms, and prevention of hypoglycemia, namely by conducting more frequent blood glucose monitoring (Kemenkes RI, 2024).

Diabetic foot ulcers are a result of peripheral neuropathy. These ulcers are caused by poor adherence to wound prevention, hygiene, and inadequate foot care. Most diabetic patients lack adequate knowledge. Therefore, health education on prevention and early detection of the causes of diabetic foot ulcers is an effective solution to reduce the number of cases of diabetic foot ulcers in diabetic patients (Santoso et al., 2023).

Diabetic foot ulcers are wounds that arise from infection or tissue damage in the feet of people with diabetes, triggered by high blood sugar that damages nerves (diabetic neuropathy) and blood vessels. Nerve damage can lead to loss of sensation, while blocked blood vessels impede blood flow. These ulcers are a leading cause of hospitalization in patients with diabetes and lead to more than one million amputations each year. Therefore, good

knowledge of type 2 diabetes prevention methods is crucial for patients with type 2 diabetes, as lack of knowledge often leads to delayed treatment and severe gangrene requiring amputation. (Rismayanti et al., 2024).

Health education is a planned and dynamic learning process to change behavior by increasing knowledge, attitudes, and skills related to a healthier lifestyle. Health promotion methods can be classified based on communication techniques, namely direct and indirect counseling, based on the number of targets, namely individual, group, and mass, based on the recipient's senses, namely seeing, hearing, and combinations such as demonstrations (Sunarti et al., 2024).

The development of information media, one of which is video, is one of the rapid developments in electronic media that is very effective for use as an educational medium due to its ability to convey learning concepts comprehensively in a short time, simplify the training process, and is considered an inexpensive and affordable medium. In various health fields, the use of educational videos has proven superior to written materials, resulting in patient satisfaction and better information acquisition (Abrar et al., 2022).

Lack of information on diabetes prevention has led to a continued surge in diabetes cases each year, from children to adults. This is due to unhealthy eating habits, such as consuming foods high in glucose. Therefore, using video as an educational tool can help convey information on the prevention and treatment of diabetic foot ulcers.

Most people with diabetes lack understanding of how to prevent and treat foot wounds, which can worsen the condition, leading to larger wounds and ultimately amputation. Based on this, researchers conducted a review of the "Effectiveness of Health Education Videos on Knowledge of Preventive Care for Foot Wounds in Diabetes Patients."

RESEARCH METHOD

This study employed a Systematic Literature Review, a methodology that involves collecting and evaluating research focused on a specific topic. The research involved determining a data search strategy or information sources through Google Scholar, then selecting them through a quality assessment using inclusion and exclusion criteria.

To limit the scope of the study, the researcher used the PICO framework to determine inclusion and exclusion criteria for the information or data used in this study.

Table 1. PICO Framework

Elemen PICO Framework	Definisi	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion criteria
Population/Populasi	The group or condition being investigated	Patients with diabetes	Not a diabetes patient
Intervention/Intervensi	The action taken, procedure or exposure being tested	Education is carried out using video media	Not getting education using Video Media
Comparison/Perbandingan	The existence of alternative actions or comparing actions as controls	There may be comparative actions (other forms of education)	n/a
Outcome/Hasil	The results measured or obtained	Effectiveness of Using Video as an Educational Media in Increasing Knowledge of Foot Wound Prevention	n/a

Gambar 1. Prism Diagram

The keyword used in the search for information sources was "The Effectiveness of Health Education Videos on Knowledge of Preventive Care for Foot Wounds in Diabetes Patients." The data obtained amounted to 365 articles, then the data was filtered according to the established criteria, the limit of articles used as data sources in this study was the last 5 years starting from 2021-2025.

RESULTS

Table 2. Results of a Review of 5 Articles on the Effectiveness of Health Education Videos on Knowledge of Preventive Care for Foot Wounds in Diabetes Patients

No.	Author's Name	Research Title	Research result	Findings
1.	(Halimah & Sutisna, 2025)	The Effect of Video Foot Care Education on Knowledge of Type II Diabetic Ulcer Prevention at Griya Puspa Wound Care Yogyakarta	Research shows that before education, 90% of respondents had poor knowledge. After education, there was a significant increase, with 93% achieving good knowledge (p-value <0.05).	<p>This study found that before receiving education, the majority of Diabetes Mellitus (DM) patients (90% of 27 out of 30 respondents) had insufficient knowledge about diabetic wound prevention. Only 10% (3 respondents) had sufficient knowledge.</p> <p>This very limited knowledge is due to a lack of exposure to adequate information about proper foot care for DM patients, such as cleaning, moisturizing, trimming nails, and preventing foot injuries. This lack of knowledge is considered a risk factor for recurrent ulcers in Type II DM patients who have previously experienced ulcers.</p> <p>Providing education using video is considered important because it plays a significant role in increasing DM patients' knowledge about their disease. The goal is to change patient behavior, help them achieve better health, and improve their quality of life.</p>
2.	(Apriani et al., 2024)	The Effect of Foot Care Education Using Video Media on Diabetic Wound Prevention Behavior in Diabetes Mellitus Patients	Respondents' behavior before and after the video education session improved, with the mean knowledge score increasing from 7.91 to 9.97. Statistical test results indicated an effect of foot care education on diabetic wound prevention behavior in patients with type 2 diabetes (p-value 0.000).	<p>Foot care education using video media has been proven effective in increasing respondents' knowledge.</p> <p>This improvement occurred because respondents paid close attention during the intervention and was supported by increased patient awareness of dietary needs. Statistically, the use of foot care educational videos demonstrated a significant difference in respondents' knowledge.</p>

3.	(Rasyida & Susanti, 2024)	The Effect of Providing Educational Videos About Diabetes Mellitus on the Level of Knowledge in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients	<p>The results of the study showed that 21 respondents had insufficient knowledge before the video was given, becoming 5 respondents after the video was given. Respondents with sufficient knowledge were 4 to 14 respondents. The number of respondents with good knowledge increased from 5 respondents to 11 respondents out of a total of 30 respondents. The results of the Paired T-Test analysis showed a large influence of 6-9 with a p value = 0.000 <math>\alpha = 0.5</math>. H1 is accepted.</p>	<p>Diabetes mellitus patients are often elderly and have little education, resulting in low levels of diabetes knowledge and a barrier to self-care.</p> <p>Given the tendency of modern society to prefer watching rather than reading, educational videos were chosen as an intervention medium. Videos are considered effective because they engage multiple senses, are easy to digest, and offer a non-boring experience.</p> <p>The results showed that providing educational videos significantly increased respondents' knowledge levels. Initially, most respondents had very low knowledge, but after watching the videos, their knowledge levels increased to moderate. This demonstrates that educational videos have a positive effect on improving patients' understanding of the disease, prevention, treatment, lifestyle, and complications.</p> <p>This increased knowledge, coupled with easy access to educational content via mobile phones and intensive learning, is expected to raise awareness among patients about early diabetes detection.</p>
4.	(Susilawati et al., 2024)	The Effect of Digital Foot Care Education on Behavioral Intentions Preventing Foot Wounds in Diabetes Mellitus Patients	<p>The results of the study showed that the behavioral intention to prevent foot wounds in diabetes patients after being provided with education through digital media in the form of video viewing in the control group was 37.5%, behavioral intention was poor in 62.5%, and behavioral intention was good in the intervention</p>	<p>Foot wound prevention education for diabetes patients was delivered using a 2-minute digital video. The video material covered important steps such as:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How to clean your feet daily. 2. The appropriate area to apply moisturizer (not between your toes).

			<p>group was 100%, indicating an increase in knowledge about foot care in preventing foot wounds.</p> <p>The results of the study in the control group were $p = 1.000$, indicating no difference in behavioral intention to prevent foot wounds in diabetes mellitus patients. Foot care education through digital media contributed positively to increasing knowledge and insight into foot care as a preventative measure for foot wounds in diabetes mellitus patients.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. How to properly trim your nails. 4. Using safe footwear. 5. First aid for minor wounds. <p>The primary goal of this education was to motivate patients to develop the knowledge and intention to independently perform preventative foot wound care.</p> <p>The results showed that the digital video education significantly increased knowledge (100% intention to perform independent foot care), confirming that knowledge is a crucial domain in shaping action.</p> <p>The advantages of using digital video as an educational medium are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It facilitates understanding due to the use of images and sound. 2. It can be used repeatedly and can be speeded up or slowed down. 3. It is highly relevant and effective because digital media is widespread and frequently used by the public in daily activities. <p>In short, digital video is a highly effective and accessible medium for increasing diabetes patients' knowledge and intention to perform self-care for their feet to prevent wounds.</p>
5.	(Chloranyta et al., 2024)	The Effect of Audiovisual Education on Knowledge of Foot Care for Type 2 Diabetes at Gedong Air Community Health	The results of the study showed that the average pre-test score was 7.27, indicating that the average score was in the poor knowledge range. The average	Health education is crucial for Diabetes Mellitus (DM) patients because it can enhance their understanding. This understanding, in turn, will improve healthy

		Center, Bandar Lampung	<p>post-test score for foot care knowledge in diabetes was between 12.97 and 13.83, categorized as good. The results of the paired t-test on the pre-test and post-test in this study showed a significant difference with a p value of 0.000. There is an effect of health education through audio-visual media on increasing knowledge about foot care in type 2 diabetes.</p>	<p>behaviors in maintaining their health and preventing serious problems such as the risk of Diabetic Foot Ulcers. The use of audiovisual media in education for Type 2 DM patients is considered effective due to its advantages:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. More Engaging Information Delivery: Information is delivered through images and sound simultaneously, engaging both the senses of hearing and sight. This captures attention and increases respondents' enthusiasm, which correlates with increased knowledge. 2. Enhances Recall: Knowledge acquisition increases due to the "recall" factor. Audiovisual media facilitates the process of recalling specific material, which is key to increasing knowledge. 3. Supports Independent Learning: Audiovisual media can be replayed repeatedly, enabling respondents to learn independently. 4. Increases Focus and Activeness: The use of this media also increases respondents' motivation and attention, enabling them to focus more on the material, become more
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DISCUSSION

Effectiveness of Health Education Videos on Knowledge of Preventive Care for Foot Wounds in Diabetic Patients

Based on the five existing studies, there are very strong similarities in findings regarding the effectiveness of using video or audiovisual/digital media as an educational intervention to increase knowledge and behavior/intention to prevent foot ulcers in diabetes patients. Here are some key points from the five scientific articles analyzed.

1. Low Initial Knowledge

The five articles consistently identified that the initial knowledge of DM patients, particularly regarding foot care and wound prevention, was in the poor to very poor range before educational interventions were provided.

- a. Halimah & Sutisna (2025) found that 90% of respondents had insufficient knowledge.
- b. Rasyida & Susanti (2024) noted that 21 out of 30 respondents had insufficient knowledge.
- c. Chloranyta et al. (2024) noted that the average initial score was in the insufficient knowledge range.

Knowledge is influenced by two factors: formal and non-formal education. The higher a person's education and experience, the broader their knowledge. (Redho & Septinawati, 2023).

This lack of knowledge is due to a lack of exposure to adequate information and is often associated with advanced age and low education levels. Furthermore, this lack of knowledge is considered a crucial risk factor for recurrent ulcers.

Changes in knowledge are influenced by a person's level of education, which influences their understanding of information. A person's level of education will influence their response to information more rationally and their consideration of the potential benefits they might derive from an idea. (Farhan et al., 2022).

2. Effectiveness of Video/Digital Media in Increasing Knowledge

All studies showed a significant increase in the level of knowledge after providing education using video/digital media, as evidenced by a p-value < 0.05 or p-value = 0.000.

- a. Halimah & Sutisna (2025) noted a dramatic increase, from 90% with insufficient knowledge to 93% with good knowledge.
- b. Rasyida & Susanti (2024) showed an increase from a majority of respondents

with insufficient knowledge to a majority with sufficient and good knowledge

- c. Apriani et al. (2024) reported a significant increase in the mean knowledge score, from 7.91 to 9.97 points.
- d. Chloranyta et al. (2024) also showed a significant increase in the average score to the good category.

Health education is an important process to empower individuals and communities to maintain, improve and protect their health, through increasing knowledge, willingness and ability (Santoso et al., 2023). This increase in knowledge is associated with the advantages of video/audiovisual media itself, such as: Involving Multiple Senses: The combination of images, sound, and visualizations attracts attention, increases enthusiasm, and facilitates understanding; Improving Recall: This media facilitates the process of recalling specific material; Accessibility and Flexibility: Videos are easy to digest, not boring, can be accessed repeatedly via mobile phones or digital media, and can be sped up/slowed down as needed. Audiovisual media is a set of tools that can project moving images and sound. The benefits of using this media are that it can attract attention and make education more interesting by using audiovisual media. (Oktaviani et al., 2021).

There was a significant influence of video education on diabetic wound prevention behavior, indicating that increased knowledge was supported by increased patient awareness. This emphasizes that increased knowledge is a crucial domain that can shape the intention to take preventive measures independently.

Audiovisual media has been proven effective and reliable in providing independent foot care for diabetes patients. Successful control of diabetic foot complications will depend on patient self-care, as >95% of diabetes treatment relies on individual confidence, ability, and adherence to health maintenance. (Agustini et al., 2024).

Overall, the primary goal of education—changing patient behavior, helping them achieve better health, and improving quality of life—has been shown to be achievable through educational video interventions. Educational video is considered an ideal medium because it leverages powerful cognitive mechanisms involved in learning, particularly in adults. Audiovisual media uniquely presents information through images, sound, and text.

3. Clinical Implications and Transformation of Self-Care

The collective findings of this study have profound clinical implications, particularly in

shifting the focus of DM care from solely treatment to active prevention and patient empowerment.

- a. The Importance of Knowledge as a Foundation for Behavior: This research demonstrates that significantly increased knowledge (Halimah & Sutisna, 2025; Rasyida & Susanti, 2024) is a key prerequisite for changing behavioral intentions and preventive actions (Susilawati et al., 2024; Apriani et al., 2024). When patients understand proper foot hygiene, proper use of moisturizer (not between the toes), proper nail trimming, and safe footwear (Susilawati et al., 2024), they shift from passive compliance to active decision-making in their daily care.
- b. Targeting Key Complications: Focusing education on foot care is highly relevant given that Diabetic Foot Ulcers are a serious complication that can lead to amputation and reduced quality of life. With increased knowledge and preventive behaviors, the risk of ulcer recurrence—a major problem for patients with Type 2 DM—can be effectively minimized.
- c. The Role of Health Facilities: The results of this study can serve as a basis for health facilities (such as community health centers and wound care centers) to integrate video media as a standard educational protocol, replacing or complementing traditional lecture methods. Audiovisual media has been shown to increase respondent motivation and focus, which directly supports the effectiveness of health education (Chloranyta et al., 2024).

To ensure the sustainability of diabetic foot care efforts, systematic follow-up is necessary. One step that can be taken is implementing an ongoing education program. Technology and social media can also be utilized to continuously educate the public, for example by sharing instructional videos or infographics about diabetic foot care. In addition to the educational aspect, strengthening the monitoring and evaluation system is also necessary to ensure that participants continue to apply the skills they have learned (Ismail et al., 2025).

The success of this educational program is determined by the quality of the video, both in terms of the content and the visualization using animations or real people that reflect reality. A clear and focused video flow will make it easier for diabetes patients to absorb the message conveyed through the educational video.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results obtained, it can be concluded that collectively, educational videos or digital/audiovisual media are highly effective and relevant intervention methods for increasing knowledge and behavioral intentions to prevent foot ulcers in patients. This increased understanding is key to triggering patient awareness and ability to perform self-care, which ultimately reduces the risk of serious complications such as diabetic foot ulcers.

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